

REBOOT

EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

International Workshop on Music for Film and Visual Media

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

Grant Agreement: 101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01

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1 Project Summary

This project aims to connect the existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of 'measuring', 'analysing', and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. On the other hand, the project aspires to place attention to the active preparation for the future in the area of audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only the 'what is' but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' with fresh lenses. REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action for the optimisation of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the EU in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VOD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

2 WHAT WAS DONE- ACTIONS UNDERTAKEN

In the context of global digital transformation, including now powerful AI's tools, the question of creativity is central in music for media and film. Besides, within the European market situation, composers are challenged by different types of composing situations (buyout contracts, Databank,

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editors). If being involved at the early phase of the project remains fundamental (see Hellégouarch, 2020), dealing with music creative processes considered as a workflow (including software used, from early idea to final orchestra recordings) can help young composers be more competitive, better understand the different steps from the very first idea to the final editing process and gain time. We submit a survey to a panel of young composers, and at the same time, two selected composers have been observed while composing, through an ethnographic approach (see McGrath and Love, 2017), by using different tools (screen recordings, interviews, self commentaries) for their ongoing projects. The creative process is compared with the responses provided by the entire panel of respondents in order to define the production phases. The results will then determine both the invariants of music production for media and the specificities and remediation strategies that composers develop to optimize their workflow and their competitiveness.

The recent reports from the Society for European Composers and Songwriter Alliance¹ shows a need for considering the situation of audiovisual composers, giving the nature of contracts they have, and the new challenge of AI in music creation. Music is now fully integrated in the process of the film industry with its different phases: first draft and ideas with the director and the film production, the *command*, the deliverable, the editing and mixing. The competitiveness concerns the costs of course, but also the time used to deliver a proper draft of the music. At the same time, as part of the audiovisual media, the music composed is also a consumer good, with both economic and cultural value (see Rostam Neuwirth, *in Ward* 2008). The music workflow integrates these dimensions, as it will integrate both cultural and individual choices, as well as qualitative contents that become economic value - or not. This is why analyzing this workflow - i.e. the creative process - is now fundamental.

This workflow of music composition for media is today complex as Steven Saltzman recalls (Saltzman, 2017) involving several skills or different steps (Saltzman's book *Music Editing for film and Television* (2017) details important phases of the workflow). We propose to identify these phases). Whether for mixing, post-production or even music creation, many digital tools are used by composers, starting with the Digital Audio Workstation. This raises a number of questions: which software? Which plug-in? For which result? Is there a certain number or type of plug-in that is used more or less frequently, depending on the phase of creation? Are the sounds linked to

¹ <https://composeralliance.org/>

digital tools, whether as a founding or production element? The composer is not always the project's mixer, and sometimes has to delegate this phase. On the other hand, delivery comes after the mixing phase, in the form of a stem file containing all the music files.

Finally, the last set of information we feel is necessary relates more specifically to the economic environment. A film or audiovisual project requires investment in all the fields involved, and music is no exception. These considerations can also be a constraint, particularly when it comes to the possibility of recording real instrumentalists versus virtual instruments, and have a potential impact on the creative process, as we'll see in our final section. The other essential economic aspect for creators is that of payment for their work, through royalties or other forms of remuneration.

In order to define a standard music workflow in the field of music scoring for visual media, we choose to set a qualitative survey. The panel of composers interviewed consists of 19 people and is divided into 10 professionals, including one composer "AAA" living and working in Los Angeles, and 9 students. Professionals were approached through a survey with FAMES orchestra². The majority are men, with only one professional female composer and two female students. This figure reflects a sector still largely dominated by men. In France in 2022, according to the CNC³, the proportion of women in the musical field was 31.9% for audiovisual fiction works, and that same year, there were only "11% of women composers for screen music, with women representing only 16% of those receiving authors' rights at Sacem. Only 15% of the recipients of Sacem (Society of Authors, Composers, and Publishers of Music) support were women⁴." This figure drops further (7%) for exclusively or predominantly French productions, revealing a small proportion of female composers among the 355 films⁵. In France, the collective Troisième Autrice, founded by composer Julie Roué, offers a "space created and developed by and for composers of screen music, aimed at making their work visible, supporting careers, and creating a solidarity space for exchanges, sharing knowledge, and experiences⁶".

In the field of classical or art music, the methods of analysis and critical genetics regarding the processes of composition and creation are well established today (Donin, Campos, Friedman) and allow for the development of methodologies primarily based on texts and paratexts (in the sense of

² <https://fames-project.com/>

³ <https://www.cnc.fr/documents/36995/1872922/Observatoire+de+l%E2%80%99%C3%A9galit%C3%A9+Femmes+-+Homes.pdf/4a019696-ae1f-dec2-e3a5-80e58a032e47?t=1700840730053>

⁴ <https://information.tv5monde.com/terriennes/musiques-de-cinema-les-compositrices-veulent-se-faire-entendre-1900261>

⁵ <https://www.cinezik.org/infos/affinfo.php?titre0=20230224174947>

⁶ <https://collectiftroisiemeautrice.com/a-propos/>

Genette, see Trubert, 2006). However, when it comes to considering current music production and editing techniques, particularly for film music, little literature is dedicated to the question. It is possible to connect different steps of what we can call the “traditional” way of composing music with the needs of the film industry, namely the command from the Film direction and the different way and back between the film direction team and the composer. Besides, nowadays, the music composer is very frequently also responsible for the score and the editing and the mix phase (namely the moment where all tracks from different instruments are mixed to set a whole) and the post-production too (the phase where all frequencies are calibrated), and he or she often develops its own originality through the quality of software used and the quality of virtual instruments used. The use of the music psychoacoustic effects in media needs to mix electronic music and FX (like in marvel Avengers for an example) and classical orchestra recordings - taking for granted that since big success like Star Wars, symphonic music regain interest in many film original soundtracks.

In light of this situation, we have decided, as part of the REBOOT project, to organize an international workshop on the processes of creation in the production of music for media and visuals. It is focused on issues primarily related to the initial stages of creation and work methodologies. The main idea is to conduct a methodological seminar on the workflows of music creation for visuals, to compare different approaches.

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3 THE WORKSHOP

Fig 1. Poster of the Workshop

To conduct a workshop based on an inclusive vision, we chose to invite two composers, taking advantage of a partnership between the University Côte d'Azur, La Napoule Art Foundation, and the Casaciné artist residency program. The two invited composers were Damien Scholl from Germany and Marisol Cao Milan from Cuba/Spain.

Damian Scholl is a composer of Contemporary Music and Film Music.

Born and raised in rural Franconia, he began studying violin at an early age.

From the very beginning of his musical education he had a keen interest in composing and performing his own music.

Scholl continued to pursue his interest in composition by enrolling in the University of the Arts (UdK) Berlin, where he studied from 2008 to 2013 with Walter Zimmermann. During his years at the UdK, Scholl also studied with David Fennessy at the Royal Conservatoire of Scotland in Glasgow. After his graduation he went on to study Film Music at the Film University Potsdam-Babelsberg, where he finished his academic education in 2017.

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In 2014, Scholl was awarded a scholarship to work and live in the Villa Wasmuth near Bonn. The following year, he won the Deutscher Musikwettbewerb competition (for his piece *Ghostbird*) as well as the WDR Filmscore Award. In 2017, he was invited to the AYE Composer's Week in Bangkok mentored by Dieter Mack, Peter Veale and Anothai Nitibhon.

His *Orfeo reflections*, a full-length work commissioned by Kissinger Sommer starring Lena Belkina as a soloist, has received standing ovations and critical acclaim.

Scholl has received numerous commissions – among others from Deutschlandfunk, WDR Funkhausorchester, Deutscher Musikrat, Ludwigsburger Schlossfestspiele and Linos Piano Trio.

Damian Scholl's oeuvre to this date includes works for solo instruments and small chamber ensembles, as well as bigger works including a chamber opera and works for symphonic orchestra.

Scholl is an Alumnus of the notable scholarship Studienstiftung des deutschen Volkes and a member of the German Film Academy.

Marisol Cao Milan (Havana, Cuba 1990) Orchestra Conductor, Sound Designer and Music Composer for Cinema, Audiovisuals, New Medias and Performative Arts. Graduated in Choral Conducting at the National School of Art (ENA) in Orchestral Conducting, University of the Arts (ISA) and in Sound Direction at the International Film and Television School (EICTV, in San Antonio de los Baños) in Cuba. She was selected to participate in the Castello Errante Film Residency 4th edition, 2020 in Italy and for the Media Sound Hamburg Summer School (MSH) in Germany 2021. Also, she participated in the Program for women composers and sound designers No Fixed Mix of String and Tins Sound Studio, UK 2021. Scholarship: String and Tins, Izotope and Avid Protools. She was chosen to participate in the Guadalajara Talent, 2023 in Mexico. She has collaborated with plastic artists for her installations, such as Patricia Belli, as well as on other projects in development. She performed in a visual arts project, creating live music accompanying restored and rescued analog tapes for The Light of Masao Nakagawa macro-project that includes exhibitions. She often works on the development of fictions, documentaries and new media projects working as sound director and composer at Estudios Amarras where she has collaborated with international directors on films that have been presented at prestigious festivals (IDFA; Visions du Réel; Ji.hlava; San Sebastian Film Festival; Goya...).

The workshop program was developed in consultation with the composers. The initial goal was to present the key stages of musical composition. Following that, three presentations were given to first provide a general overview of composition, its stages, and the workflow. Then, the two

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composers discussed their respective approaches to musical composition. The first session highlighted how the production project is assimilated by the composers and how they translate the emotions and different stages of the scenario into music.

PROGRAM am

Room : Ciné-club

in collaboration with Casa ciné

- **9h45 : Reception**

- **10h : Opening presentation Julie Mansion-Vaquié, Jean-François Trubert**
« How shall we combine constraints from the production and creative process ? »

- **10h30 : Marisol Cao Milan (Spain/Cuba)**
« Developing new projects : being involved at early stage ? »

- **11h : Damian Scholl (Germany)**
« Starting like Chopin or like Beethoven ? Improvising or hearing first ? »

- **11h30 : opening discussion** with the students of MSc Music Scoring for Visual Media and So Design

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Fig.2 Agenda of the Workshop

The core of the process is to examine the concepts related to the initial phases of creation. This involves comparing two fundamental processes: one that attempts an empirical approach through trial and error (improvisation) and another that takes an immediate conceptual approach based on the project's overview. This is why we worked on a co-constructed vision with two perspectives, also ensuring gender inclusivity.

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PROGRAM pm

Room : Ciné-club / studio Dolby Atmos

- **14h :Creative Jam : let's create from scratch.**

Students show their crafts in creative process.

- **15h : Workshop and Showcase**

- **16h30: Happy hour**

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Fig. 3 Agenda of the Workshop

The second stage of the workshop invited 20 students from the Master's program in Music for the Screen and Sound Design to participate and interact with the composers. The idea was to conduct a creation workshop in a hackathon style for musical creation for visuals, as well as exchange sessions focused on the musical creations already completed by the students.

4 NEXT STEP

The main results of the workshop show that the various phases of the musical creation workflow conducted within the framework of task 5.4 of WP5 were validated by the speakers and participants of the workshop. Questions related to budgets and processes were also validated. However, more interesting elements were highlighted by the composers in relation to production. Firstly, they noted that it is not necessary to fill the entire timeline with musical sound. It is essential to rethink the soundtrack in relation to the modernity of today's musical creation, and for example, the idea of continuous melody is no longer relevant. Finally, while production is always "right," it is crucial for each composer to establish a musical identity that is both aesthetic and procedural.

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